

1 **Gpr141 is a marker of coronary disease activity in humans with high CRP.**

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6 Identifying markers of heart disease in the blood facilitates detection and clinical intervention in humans
7 with disease risk. C-reactive protein is an acute phase protein of the innate immune system, produced by
8 the liver and released into the circulation early in the immune response to a variety of sterile and
9 non-sterile triggers, during inflammatory stress. High blood CRP is a known indicator or predictor of
10 cardiovascular disease risk. It is not completely understood why high CRP denotes risk of cardiovascular
11 disease. We measured total transcription in the blood of humans with very low CRP (less than 0.25) or
12 high CRP (greater than 60) to identify factors that explain elevated risk of heart disease associated with an
13 inflammatory marker. We identified high expression of the cell surface marker *Gpr141* in humans with very
14 high blood CRP levels. *Gpr141* was a marker of the foam cell, induced during differentiation from
15 macrophage. *Gpr141* is thus a marker of cardiovascular activation of the macrophage and a correlate of
16 high CRP, suggesting the biology of this G-protein cell surface receptor is relevant to heart disease in
17 humans.
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